

Using Machine Learning Methods and Electronic Health Records to Classify Patients as At-Risk for Opioid Abuse and Dependence

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Abstract—The goal of this research was to create a predictive algorithm that classifies some patients as high-risk for misuse of opioids. Opioids are often prescribed for pain relief, but can be highly addictive and lead to misuse among patients. Utilizing patient data from All of Us Research Hub, an electronic health record database, machine learning methods were applied to determine which patients were at high-risk for opioid misuse and those that were not. The models described in this paper use a patient’s drug prescription, procedures, chronic diseases, and pain history to classify whether or not a person is more likely to abuse or become dependent on opioids. The motivation for this research was to build an algorithm that medical professionals could use before prescribing a patient opioids, allowing them to consider alternative treatments if a patient is identified as at-risk for misuse. In this paper, we describe our methodology in creating a logistic regression model, decision tree, random forest, and deep learning neural network to predict a patient’s risk of opioid abuse or dependence. We were able to determine what factors impact a patient’s risk of opioid misuse the most, which were supported by prior literature review. This work demonstrates how machine learning methods such as deep learning are an important strategy when dealing with major healthcare issues such as the opioid epidemic.

I. INTRODUCTION

An opioid epidemic has plagued America since the rise in opioid prescriptions in the 1990s [1]. While opioids are a helpful and necessary painkiller for many individuals, the risk of addiction is high. In a 2015 survey, it was found that around 37 percent of adults have used prescription opioids [2]. A person is at risk of developing an addiction to opioids after 3-5 days of taking a prescribed pain reliever [3]. While prescription opioids are necessary to reduce pain in many patients, their adverse effects can also be fatal or debilitating for many of these same patients. Since 2000, the rate of deaths from drug overdoses has increased 137 percent with a 200 percent increase in the rate of deaths from overdose involving opioids [4]. Given the severity of the opioid epidemic, there is a need for action to prevent opioid misuse among patients. While opioids are considered a legitimate and sometimes necessary treatment, there are numerous risk factors that physicians need to consider before prescribing these drugs to patients. Research

demonstrates that individuals with mental health conditions like anxiety or depression are three times more likely to use opioids [5]. Additionally, economists have also found that white Americans without college degrees in rural areas have also been disproportionately impacted by the opioid epidemic. Individuals who suffer from chronic pain or have had surgical procedures also have an increased risk of persistent opioid use. The risk factors for addiction must be carefully considered when prescribing opioids, given their addictive nature.

With the rise of electronic health records, medical professionals and researchers can study real-world patient data to improve patient care, enable safer prescribing, and effectively diagnose patients [6]. An area of interest where electronic health records can be useful is predicting a patient’s risk of abusing opioids and the factors that contribute to this risk. In this paper, we will discuss our use of deep learning models for opioid misuse prediction as well as the identification of important factors that impact a patient’s risk of opioid dependence or abuse. While the medical community is often hesitant to rely on artificial intelligence to make decisions that impact individuals and their health outcomes, the use of machine learning can have some benefits in assisting medical professionals make predictions and decisions to improve patient care. Using algorithmic intelligence to make decisions gives medical professionals as much information as possible before making a decision. Medical professionals should not entirely base their decisions on algorithmic decision-making, but rather use it as a tool to understand how past cases have impacted similar patients.

In this paper, we demonstrate that deep learning methods for identifying patients as at-risk for opioid abuse or dependence outperform other baseline machine learning models such as Logistic Regression, Random Forest, and Decision Tree. Additionally, we found the most important factors that impacted a patient’s risk of opioid abuse or dependence. These risk factors were supported in our literature review of factors that impact a person’s likelihood to abuse opioids. Our work demonstrates a practical example of employing deep learning

methods for health-care problems to provide information for medical professionals who are making decisions that impact a patient’s health outlook.

II. RELATED WORKS

Our team reviewed several publications in order to study past projects using similar data and practices. The main inspiration for this paper was an experiment by Che et. al, which provided a basis for how to use deep learning techniques to classify patients on opioid use, using data from Mayo Clinic [7]. To extend this prior work, we use a different data source of electronic health records and build on the machine learning techniques used. Additionally, in preparing to use the All of Us Health database, our team consulted a paper by Harris et. al which discusses navigating the database to extract information necessary for machine learning techniques [8].

III. DATA

A. Data Source

The work in this paper was performed using data from the All of Us Health Researcher Workbench. The National Institutes of Health’s All of Us Research Program is developing one of the largest biomedical data resources of its kind. The Research Hub stores health data from a diverse group of participants from the United States. The dataset contains over 627,000 participants and over 364,000 electronic health records. This workbench is a Cloud-based environment that holds data of various types including, survey responses, physical measurements, electronic health records, wearables, and genomics.

B. Group Identification

We identified three different groups of patients for the purpose of classification. These groups were formed using the electronic health records of each patient from the conditions table in the All of Us Health database. We identified patients who have been prescribed opioids in the past based on their electronic health records and then split these patients into groups to make some interesting observations about them. The first group of patients were identified as being opioid dependent in the database. Another group of patients were identified as having a history of opioid abuse. Lastly, a group of patients with no history of opioid dependence or abuse was identified based on the data from All of Us Health. The demographics of each of these groups is shown in Table 1.

IV. FEATURE ENGINEERING

A. The Conditions Vector

To move forward with building and implementing machine learning methods, we created a vector of all conditions or diagnosis records for each patient. It was necessary to identify what kind of patient factors we needed to extract to build effective models. After some literature review, we decided to collect data on patients with the following conditions: depression, alcoholism, substance abuse, bipolar disorder, anxiety, chronic pain, schizophrenia, opioid abuse, opioid dependence, and opioid withdrawal. In order to extract patients with these conditions,

we used the All of Us Health Researcher Workbench to create a concept set of these conditions to use in our analysis. In a Python Jupyter notebook we loaded in this data and created a dataframe with the conditions of interest and unique patient IDs. If a patient had ever had one of these conditions based on their electronic health records, they were assigned a value of 1, indicating a particular condition was present for that patient. If a patient had no history of a particular condition, they were assigned a 0, indicating a particular condition was not present for that patient. The final table contained each unique patient and their presence or absence of certain conditions. This resulted in a unique vector of 1s and 0s for each patient in the dataframe.

B. The Procedures Vector

In order to create a more robust model, it was essential to include other potential risk factors for a patient’s opioid misuse. Our research found that surgical procedures that often result in opioid prescriptions can have a large impact on a person’s opioid dependence or abuse status. We decided to collect data on patients with the following procedures: immunizations, mammographies, head or neck, knee, tooth, brain, hip, vascular, and heart. Similar to the conditions vector methodology, we used the All of Us Health Researcher Workbench to create a concept set of these procedures to use in our analysis. In a Python Jupyter notebook we loaded in this data and created a dataframe with the procedures of interest and unique patient IDs. If a patient had ever had one of these procedures based on their electronic health records, they were assigned a value of 1, indicating a particular procedure was present for that patient. If a patient had no history of a particular procedure, they were assigned a 0, indicating the absence of that procedure. The final table contained each unique patient and their presence or absence of certain procedures. This resulted in a unique vector of 1s and 0s for each patient in the dataframe.

C. The Prescriptions Vector

Following the same methodology for the other vectors, we created a prescription vector for the unique patients, identifying the absence or presence of various opioid medications. We collected data on patients with the following prescriptions: natural Opium Alkaloids, Phenylpiperidine derivatives, Enzomorphans derivatives, Oripavine derivatives, and Morphinan Derivatives. We used the All of Us Health Researcher Workbench to create a concept set of these prescriptions to use in our analysis. In a Python Jupyter notebook we loaded in this data and created a dataframe with the prescriptions of interest and unique patient IDs. For each opioid prescription, the number of times a unique patient was prescribed that same medication was recorded. For example, if patient 5 was prescribed Morphine 3 different times in the database, they received a value of 3 for the Morphine column.

D. Feature Selection

In order to remove features with little significance in predicting opioid abuse or dependence, a Lasso regression was

		OPIOID DEPENDENCE		OPIOID ABUSE		ALL	
		Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage
GENDER	Total Number of Patients	7336	4.2%	4573	2.7%	174199	---
	Men	3476	47%	2501	56%	59585	34%
	Women	3544	48%	1877	42%	105959	61%
	Other/Unknown	316	4%	195	4%	5892	3%
AGE	18 and younger	---	---	---	---	---	---
	19-29	159	2%	149	3%	7765	4%
	30-49	2547	35%	1754	38%	46095	27%
	50-64	2775	38%	1705	37%	49346	29%
	64+	1855	25%	956	21%	68230	4%
RACE	White	3946	54%	2067	45%	96646	56%
	Black or African American	1771	24%	1384	30%	32469	19%
	Asian	36	5%	22	0.05%	3486	2%
	Other/Unknown	2033	27%	1100	24%	38835	23%
PATIENT HISTORY	No history of BPD	5474	74%	3255	71%	158649	93%
	History of BPD	1873	26%	1318	29%	12787	7%
	No history of Alcoholism	5052	69%	2799	61%	155902	91%
	History of Alcoholism	2284	31%	1744	38%	15534	9%
	No history of Depression	4070	55%	2397	52%	116991	68%
	History of Depression	3266	45%	2176	48%	54445	32%
	No history of Anxiety	2681	37%	1875	41%	105391	61%
	History of Anxiety	4655	63%	2698	59%	66045	39%

Fig. 1: The above table shows demographic information that was extracted from the All of Us Health database used for this project. Specifically, this is a conglomerate of all patients that had been prescribed opioids from their doctor as indicated by the All of Us Health Database. There are many insights that we obtained from this table of demographics. The first thing we noticed within the demographics table is that while the dataset as a whole contains more women, the percent of men and women that abuse opioids are about even. Additionally, the percent of men that are dependent on opioids is much higher than for women. This contrasts past research that claims women are more likely to abuse opioids than men [9]. The demographics table also demonstrates the disparities regarding race and opioid abuse or dependence. This is an insight we were expecting as many papers discuss the increase in opioid abuse and dependence among non-hispanic black communities [10]. Another interesting insight demonstrated from the demographics is that people with a history of anxiety are much more likely to become both dependent on and addicted to opioids.

performed. This Lasso regression found two predictors to be insignificant: the prescription tapentadol and a vascular procedure. To confirm the insignificance of these predictors, the full and reduced models were compared and the reduced model performed better. The reduced model that was used throughout the project included 33 variables, which were from combining the conditions, procedures, and prescriptions vectors. The final dataframe used for analysis contained a unique patient ID for each patient and the risk factors from the three vectors. These features were chosen to be strong indicators of a person's risk of opioid abuse or dependence.

E. Survey Data

In order to implement a hurdle model, which we expand on later in this paper, and to understand more about why certain patients could be considered high or low risk of opioid misuse, we explored their responses to some survey questions in the database. Based on literature review, we discovered factors like location, economic status, education, and healthcare access can have an impact on a person's risk of opioid misuse. We collected data on survey responses for questions about a patient's neighborhood, income, education level, and healthcare access. We used the All of Us Health Researcher Workbench

to create a concept set of these survey responses to use in our analysis. In a Python Jupyter notebook we loaded in this data and created a dataframe with the survey questions of interest and unique patient IDs. These features were engineered with labels 0 or 1 based on a patient's response to a particular question. In addition to these responses, we included a patient's response to a question regarding their pain level for the past 7 days. Their pain level was recorded on a scale from 1-10.

F. Undersampling

One issue that we encountered when working with our final dataset was the imbalance of classes for patients who abused or depended on opioids and those who did not. The class for non-opioid misuse patients was much larger than the class for opioid misuse patients. Since the class distribution was so different, issues arose when fitting the models. The accuracy was very high, but the recall was very low. This meant that our models had many false negatives, which can be detrimental in medical decision-making. As a result, random undersampling was implemented on the data where the majority class instances were discarded at random until a more balanced distribution was reached. More specifically, within the train set, the class of people without opioid abuse or dependence was randomly sampled from to make the size more even to that of the original train dataset. Random undersampling was executed using the 'imblearn' package in Python. Random undersampling was selected over nearest neighbors and other types of undersampling since we wanted to randomly select patients to keep in the train set.

V. MODELS

A. Random Forest

For our work, we implemented three different supervised machine learning models and compared the results of these. These models were a Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, and Random Forest. After analyzing the results of these models, the Random Forest was preferred given that it had the highest recall among all of the supervised models. The variables used in the Random Forest are each patient's conditions, prescriptions, and procedures that were identified as important after feature selection. The model was created using the Python Scikit-learn package's Random Forest Classifier with 10 estimators. Only 10 estimators were selected as adding more estimators decreased the model's efficiency and did not significantly increase the model's accuracy or recall. The model was trained on 60 percent of the data and tested on the other 40 percent. In the final model selection, the best-performing random forest model filtered out low risk patients with a Logistic regression model and then implemented the random forest on the remaining patients. Specific accuracy metrics for each model implementation are discussed in the model performance section below.

B. Deep Learning

While random forest was a strong baseline model, we wanted to implement a more complex model to better predict a patient's risk of opioid abuse or dependence. We used a Deep

Neural Network. These models have significant advantages in extracting features at different levels of abstraction and thereby learning more complex patterns. A deep neural network (DNN) is an artificial neural network (ANN) with multiple hidden layers between the input and output layers. A DNN model is made up of multiple non-linear transformation layers. The output of each layer is fed to the next layer as input. To implement a deep learning model on the data, we used the Python Keras package. We created a Sequential model, adding layers one at a time to get the best network structure. The rectified linear unit (ReLU) function is used as the non-linear transformation for each hidden layer. This function does not suffer from the vanishing gradient problem during training compared to other non-linear transformations. To make a binary classification in the output layer, we applied a sigmoid function in the last layer and set the output dimension to be 1, classifying a patient's risk of opioid misuse. With this DNN structure, the model learned the node weights by optimizing binary cross-entropy loss function during training. In our implementation of a DNN model, we compared the performance of three different model structures with one, two, and three hidden layers. Similar to our prior discussion, we focused on optimizing the recall value. Ultimately, we found that the deep learning model with 2 hidden layers performed the best after randomly undersampling the train set. The result metrics for the deep learning models are included in figure 2.

C. Hurdle Model

Hurdle models are a class of models that can handle data imbalance, specifically when a target data has many of one value, usually zero [11]. An additional solution to the problem of class imbalance of patients who misused and did not misuse opioids within the data was to create a hurdle model to eliminate patients that we were confident would not misuse opioids. For this hurdle model, we utilized the survey data about patient income, health insurance, pain level, and more to give an initial prediction of patients' risk for opioid abuse or dependence, identifying those that were very unlikely to misuse opioids. We used three baseline models in an attempt to classify the no-risk patient group in the data. The models used were Logistic Regression, Random Forest, and Decision Tree. The Logistic Regression model was able to accurately eliminate about 68,000 no-risk patients. After removing these patients from our original dataset, this data was used in the original Random Forest and Deep Learning models. The Random Forest did improve performance after the elimination of this group of patients, but the deep learning model did not. While a hurdle model was a unique approach to data refinement, we found random undersampling to be the most effective approach in rebalancing the classes of patients.

D. Model Performance

The performance of each model we executed is shown in Table 2. As previously mentioned, the main metric of interest was recall. We focused on optimizing recall, because it was critical to minimize false negatives recall so patients with a

TRAINING METHOD	METRIC	BASELINE MODELS			DEEP MODELS		
		LR	DT	RF	1HL	2HL	3HL
ORIGINAL	Accuracy	0.97	0.93	0.88	0.99	0.99	0.75
	Precision	0.51	0.34	0.32	0.69	0.77	0.75
	Recall	0.31	0.36	0.56	0.28	0.23	0.26
UNDERSAMPLING	Accuracy	0.78	0.58	0.63	0.85	0.84	0.87
	Precision	0.22	0.12	0.15	0.84	0.83	0.86
	Recall	0.68	0.73	0.81	0.73	0.75	0.70
HURDLE MODEL	Accuracy	0.87	--	--	--	--	--
	Precision	0.4	--	--	--	--	--
	Recall	0.99	--	---	--	--	--
FILTERED USING HURDLE MODEL FIRST	Accuracy	0.74	0.72	0.71	0.9	0.89	0.93
	Precision	0.67	0.66	0.67	0.82	0.79	0.85
	Recall	0.66	0.65	0.75	0.48	0.39	0.38

Fig. 2: The accuracy, precision, and recall of each model we ran are included in the figure above.

high risk of opioid abuse or dependence were classified as such. It was also important to have acceptable accuracy and precision values as all patients should not be classified as at-risk for opioid misuse. The best baseline supervised model was the random forest that eliminated very low-risk patients with the hurdle model before it was executed. This model has a high recall while also keeping the accuracy and precision high. The best deep learning model was the model with 2 hidden layers and randomly undersampled data. The recall was high as well as reasonable values for accuracy and precision.

VI. VARIABLE IMPORTANCE

A. Measure of Importance: Shapley Values

In order to determine which features were the most important in predicting a patient’s risk of opioid abuse or dependence, Shapley values for each feature were calculated. Shapley values measure how much each feature value contributed to the prediction compared to the average prediction [12]. Shapley values can be calculated for features in various machine learning models including tree methods and deep learning neural networks. We utilized the SHAP library in Python which has optimized functions for interpreting tree-based and deep learning models, explaining how much each feature contributes to the model’s prediction [13]. The SHAP package also has

the ability to visualize the important features from a model. We produced a mean SHAP bar graph, calculating the mean SHAP value for each feature across all observations. This bar graph displayed the most important features for each of the models. For both the baseline random forest model and the deep learning model, the five most important features were buprenorphine prescriptions, naloxone prescriptions, substance abuse, alcoholism, and chronic pain. Other important features included opioid prescriptions such as fentanyl and morphine as well as conditions like bipolar disorder and anxiety. Many of these important features were ones that we expected from prior research.

B. Impact of Quantization

One issue in working with survey data is the issue of quantization which is the process of mapping continuous infinite values to a smaller set of discrete finite values [14]. Quantization introduces sources of error in the algorithm such as rounding errors, underflow or overflow, computational noise, and limit cycles. When working with survey responses with several different responses, we created a threshold for several variables to make the value binary, a 0 or 1. For example, the income variable was set as a 0 for patients with less than \$50,000 annual household income and 1 for above. In

addition, several survey questions allowed responses on a scale of strongly agree, agree, neutral, etc. We classified the response strongly agree and agree as 1 and the other responses as 0.

Another impact of quantization on the data was the pain variable in the survey data. This question asked participants to rate their pain on a scale from 0-10 in the past 7 days. This creates the problem of quantization because it is a subjective variable. For example, two patients could rate a very different level of pain as the same based on their pain tolerance that day. In order to understand the impact of this quantization error, we performed a sensitivity analysis on this variable. We found that a patient's pain level decreasing or increasing by one did not typically change their classification. Although, when a patient's pain level increased dramatically, they were more likely to be classified as at risk for opioid abuse or dependence.

VII. FUTURE WORKS

This paper outlines the work and efforts of our team to create and implement machine learning models to predict a person's risk of opioid abuse or dependence. In future work, we can explore temporal or sequential data to explore a patient's history and risk of opioid misuse over time. A Recurrent Neural Network could be implemented as these deep learning models can handle sequential or temporal data and are able to memorize what they have seen before and benefit from shared model weights for all time steps. If physicians can recognize patterns of opioid misuse and predict a patient's opioid usage timeline, they can understand when a patient could become addicted and take steps to avoid this event. Medical professionals must find ways to combat the opioid epidemic, and machine learning methods have the potential to be incredibly helpful in the future.

VIII. CONCLUSION

As outlined in this paper, our team developed various machine learning models to classify patients as at-risk or not-at-risk for opioid abuse or dependence. After data processing and feature engineering, the baseline models were created and tested. The random forest with the elimination of a group of patients proved to be the best-performing model out of the baseline models. The best deep learning model proved to be the two hidden layer model with the data randomly undersampled to balance the classes of patients effectively. This deep learning model maintained a high accuracy, precision, and recall throughout the training and testing process. The most important features were identified for the models, backed by prior research on risk factors for patients prescribed opioids. Ultimately, our work demonstrates how machine learning models, specifically deep learning neural networks, have the potential to utilize electronic health records to help make informed medical decisions. These methods can be a powerful tool to combat medical crises, such as the opioid epidemic.

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